

A note on predator-prey dynamics in radiocarbon datasets

Nimrod Marom*¹ , Uri Wolkowski¹

¹ Laboratory of Archaeozoology, University of Haifa, Haifa, Israel.

*Corresponding author

Correspondence: nmarom2@univ.haifa.ac.il

ABSTRACT

Predator-prey interactions have been a central theme in population ecology for the past century, but real-world data sets only exist for recent, relatively short (<100 years) time spans. This limits our ability to study centennial/millennial-scale predator-prey dynamics. We propose that regional radiocarbon databases can be used to reconstruct a signal of predator-prey population dynamics in deep time, overcoming this limitation. We support our argument with examples from Pleistocene Beringia and the Holocene Judean Desert.

Keywords: radiocarbon, paleozoology, Judean Desert, Beringia.

Appendices

Supplementary table 1. The Beringia dataset, from Fox-Dobbs et al. (2008, tables 2-3)

<u>Genus</u>	<u>Specimen ID</u>	<u>RC date</u>	<u>RC error</u>	<u>Lab ID</u>
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 30450	7751	64	AA48695
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67165	12600	150	AA42317
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67157	14690	190	AA42315
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 70944	15268	169	AA38449
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 30447	15580	190	AA35223
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 30451	15800	90	UCR3761
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67227	15870	190	AA35231
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 68009-A	16800	210	AA35227
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67224	17640	240	AA35226
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 30432	17670	230	AA48704
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 30453	19210	260	AA48702
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 70942	20150	110	CAMS115775
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67169	20305	385	AA35216A
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 30452	20550	120	CAMS115769
<i>Canis</i>	CMN 9929	20910	70	UCR3764
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67231	21900	140	CAMS115774
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 68008-G	23380	470	AA35222
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67170	27620	580	AA48694
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 30431	28500	300	CAMS115776
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67248	29800	400	CAMS115773
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67168	31200	450	CAMS115767
<i>Canis</i>	CMN 42388	33900	1700	CAMS115763
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:A 67184	34600	700	CAMS115763
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67159	35200	2300	AA48703

<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 70958	37700	2600	AA37615
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 70945	37733	2633	AA38448
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67202	38000	2700	AA35224
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67243	38500	1100	CAMS115772
<i>Canis</i>	CMN 17311	38790	540	UCR3762
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67197	39300	1230	CAMS115760
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67208	41040	1530	CAMS115759
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 30438	45500	2700	CAMS115778
<i>Canis</i>	AMNH F:AM 67167	45800	2800	CAMS115768
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142429	12310	45	CAMS119982
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142423	12560	50	CAMS119976
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60025	13710	60	CAMS120061
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60005	14630	60	CAMS119969
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142421	14860	60	CAMS119974
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142424	15460	70	CAMS119977
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60032	15850	70	CAMS120068
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60004	16370	80	CAMS119968
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60044	18630	100	CAMS119970
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60023	19000	100	CAMS120058
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60027	19590	110	CAMS120059
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142420	19870	110	CAMS119973
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142430	19950	110	CAMS119983
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60020	19950	120	CAMS120062
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142427	19960	110	CAMS119980
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142426	20300	120	CAMS119979
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142425	20440	120	CAMS119978
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142419	20520	120	CAMS119971
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142428	21280	130	CAMS119981
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60026	21310	140	CAMS120060

<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142435	21840	140	CAMS119989
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142434	22610	150	CAMS119988
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60003	24260	200	CAMS120077
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142431	25710	230	CAMS119985
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 142433	25960	240	CAMS119987
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60033	39910	1330	CAMS120069
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60017	41000	1500	CAMS119972
<i>Equus</i>	AMNH F:AM 60221	43700	200	CAMS120067
<i>Rangifer</i>	AMNH F:AM 142443	16000	190	AA48686
<i>Rangifer</i>	AMNH F:AM 142444	16400	202	AA48687
<i>Rangifer</i>	AMNH F:AM 142440	16700	207	AA48682
<i>Rangifer</i>	AMNH F:AM 142441	17300	222	AA48683
<i>Rangifer</i>	AMNH F:AM 142438	21000	361	AA48680
<i>Rangifer</i>	AMNH F:AM 142446	29640	370	CAMS120070

Supplementary table 2. The Judean Desert Holocene dataset, modified from Lazagabaster et al. (2022).

Genus	Specimen_ID	Material	RCdate	RCerror	Laboratory	Lab_ID
Panthera	HE-004	collagen	5317	25	OxA	39091
Panthera	HE-008	collagen	5301	25	OxA	39214
Panthera	HE-010	collagen	4477	26	OxA	38732
Panthera	HE-053	collagen	4508	30	OxA	38788
Panthera	HE-054	collagen	6239	26	OxA	39216
Panthera	HE-124	collagen	5375	28	OxA	47465
Panthera	HE-195	collagen	4945	25	OxA	39107
Panthera	HE-230	collagen	4935	26	OxA	39109
Panthera	HE-231	collagen	5312	25	OxA	39110
Panthera	HE-232	collagen	5366	30	OxA	47473
Panthera	SK-703	bioapatite	3200	30	UGAMS	44190
Panthera	UR-035	bioapatite	8960	30	UGAMS	48266
Capra	EG-002	bioapatite	7850	30	UGAMS	46061
Capra	HE-021	collagen	3141	22	OxA	39215
Capra	HE-024	collagen	1860	20	UGAMS	46066
Capra	QN-028	collagen	1870	20	OxA	39255
Capra	QN-083	collagen	4550	24	OxA	39175
Capra	SK-014	collagen	350	20	UGAMS	46081
Capra	TS-022	collagen	1338	20	OxA	39227
Capra	QN-084	collagen	4520	20	UGAMS	46078
Capra	TZB-004	collagen	870	20	UGAMS	48253
Capra	TS-032	collagen	1060	20	UGAMS	46116
Procavia	ARN-001	collagen	180	20	UGAMS	48283
Procavia	ARN-002	bioapatite	9600	110	UGAMS	48284
Procavia	C513-003	collagen	430	20	UGAMS	48261
Procavia	C513-004	collagen	1490	20	UGAMS	48260
Procavia	EG-009	collagen	7141	28	OxA	-88

Procavia	HE-005	collagen	2948	22	OxA	39213
Procavia	HE-100	collagen	2920	20	UGAMS	46068
Procavia	HE-153	collagen	6476	26	OxA	39218
Procavia	HE-177	bioapatite	4350	20	UGAMS	46069
Procavia	HE-184	collagen	2920	22	OxA	39106
Procavia	HYS-002	collagen	1130	20	UGAMS	49003
Procavia	HYS-003	collagen	1280	20	UGAMS	49004
Procavia	QN-026	collagen	924	19	OxA	39255
Procavia	QN-038	collagen	2520	30	UGAMS	46077
Procavia	QN-056	collagen	1144	20	OxA	39260
Procavia	QN-087	collagen	335	20	OxA	39176
Procavia	SK-001	collagen	363	22	OxA	39607
Procavia	SK-002	collagen	376	19	OxA	39608
Procavia	SK-046	collagen	1590	20	OxA	39609
Procavia	SK-152	bioapatite	6490	30	UGAMS	46134
Procavia	SK-189	collagen	1140	20	UGAMS	46085
Procavia	SK-211	collagen	4228	24	OxA	39930
Procavia	SK-241	collagen	620	18	OxA	39615
Procavia	SK-493	collagen	646	18	OxA	39849
Procavia	TS-065	collagen	1160	19	OxA	47371
Procavia	TZB-009	collagen	2010	20	UGAMS	48251
Procavia	YO-013	collagen	721	18	OxA	39851

References

- Fox-Dobbs, K., Leonard, J.A., Koch, P.L., 2008. Pleistocene megafauna from eastern Beringia: Paleoecological and paleoenvironmental interpretations of stable carbon and nitrogen isotope and radiocarbon records. *Palaeogeogr. Palaeoclimatol. Palaeoecol.* 261, 30–46.
- Lazagabaster, I.A., Égüez, N., Ullman, M., Porat, R., Wachtel, I., Davidovich, U., Marom, N., 2022. Cave paleozoology in the Judean Desert: assembling records of Holocene wild mammal communities. *J. Quat. Sci.* 37, 651–663.
- Leonard, J.A., Vilà, C., Fox-Dobbs, K., Koch, P.L., Wayne, R.K., Van Valkenburgh, B., 2007. Megafaunal Extinctions and the Disappearance of a Specialized Wolf Ecomorph. *Current Biology* 17, 1146-1150.

